

Budget

Proposal: TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

Budget item	Number of items	Cost per item (net)	Total cost (net)	Total cost (gross)
Expert Project Manager - monthly labor	9	€700.00	€6,300.00	€8,568.00
Four Expert Project Consultants - monthly labor	36	€300.00	€10,800.00	€14,688.00
Repository Website Building	1	€600.00	€600.00	€816.00
Repository Website Hosting for 3 years	1	€168.67	€168.67	€168.67
Repository Search and Download Interface Building	1	€1,000.00	€1,000.00	€1,360.00
Repository Search and Download Interface Training for the Team	1	€400.00	€400.00	€544.00
Repository Search and Download Interface Hosting for 6 years	1	€2,868.07	€2,868.07	€2,868.07
Three Student Project Assistants - monthly labor	24	€136.30	€3,271.12	€4,448.73
CoreTrustSeal application	1	€1,000.00	€1,000.00	€1,000.00
Zoom Pro account for one year for meetings and workshops	1	€139.90	€139.90	€139.90
Attending an RDA/EOSC event (e.g. RDA Plenary Meeting, EOSC Symposium) abroad	1	€9,000.00	€9,000.00	€9,000.00
Expected Foreign Transaction Fees	1	€1,976.50	€1,976.50	€1,976.50
Research Overhead for the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy	1	€4,169.36	€4,169.36	€4,169.36
Total Requested Budget				€49,748.58